

TYPES OF MOTIVES WHEN CHOOSING A PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the motives for choosing a profession, the influence of various factors on the personality of a high school student and on his professional self-determination. Also, the types of motives that are decisive factors in choosing professions and meeting the needs of the individual.

The motivation for a conscious choice of a profession is a system of motives aimed at realizing the need to master a certain type of professional activity.

Motivation occupies one of the leading places in the structure of personality behavior and is one of the basic concepts used to explain the driving forces of activity in general. Motive, motivation - an incentive to the activity and activity of the subject, associated with the desire to satisfy certain needs.

In psychology, motivation refers to a set of external and internal conditions that induce the subject to activity.

An analysis of studies on the problem of motivation for choosing a profession shows a wide variety of motives that affect the effectiveness of the process of professional self-determination. Together with

economic motives, psychological motives are of great importance: self-respect, recognition from the surrounding members of the team, moral satisfaction from work.

These types of motives are based on the study of human needs, which leads to the emergence of two global theories of motivation: content and process.

According to the first approach, human needs are the main motive for behavior, and, consequently, for human activity. Proponents of this approach include American psychologists Abraham Maslow, Frederick Herzberg and David McClelland.

The second approach is based on process theories. These include the theory of expectations, or the model of motivation according to V. Vroom, the theory of justice and the model of Porter Lauer. Among

domestic scientists, the greatest success in developing the theory of motivation was achieved by L.S. Vygotsky and his students A.N. Leontiev and B.F. Lomov.

Motives for choosing a profession can be reduced to three main complexes:

1) Interest.

– Direct professional interests include:

- professional-specific interest - interest in objects, in labor processes that characterize its main functions, as well as in the results expressed in products created, services provided, etc.

- situational interest is formed on the basis of random, atypical features for this profession and is explained by the narrowness of the student's professional horizons.

– Indirect professional interests include:

- professional and cognitive interest is based on the desire to know certain natural, technical, humanitarian and other processes and phenomena.

- interest in self-education is manifested in the desire for spiritual enrichment and the formation of subjectively valuable personality traits.

- prestigious interest - the choice of a profession is determined by the prospects for professional growth, this profession provides the prestige of the profession in society.

2) Duty

The motive of public duty in choosing a profession is the student's awareness of the real social benefit from his participation in this field of activity, the experience of personal responsibility for successful work, and the readiness to overcome possible moral and physical difficulties.

There are 5 main groups of debt motives:

- Responsibility in relation to daily professional duties and requirements;

- The desire to improve skills in the chosen business;

- Innovation in work and its organization;

- Altruistic aspirations;

- General civic aspirations.

3) Self-assessment of professional suitability

The process of formation of self-assessment of professional suitability proceeds unevenly and this can be expressed in the following contradiction: either the student fails to correlate the properties of the profession known to him with his personal qualities (lack of self-knowledge), or he finds it difficult to determine the profession that corresponds to his data (lack of professional information). With age, the content of self-esteem is gradually enriched, but these changes are not a process that develops consistently and intensively.

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